

EFFECT OF BIOPHILIC STRATEGIES IN LUXURY HOTELS ON ATTENTION RESTORATION

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Abstract

In today's fast-paced world, where attention is a valuable and limited resource, the quest for respite in settings like hotels and luxury establishments has become increasingly relevant. Existing studies have underscored the many benefits of nature exposure on human health, urging the exploration of these advantages within the distinct realm of the luxury hospitality industry. This study aimed to assess the influence of integrating biophilic design strategies on attention restoration within luxury hotels in Nigeria. Through a random sampling method, 415 responses were gathered from Nigerian hotel guests with the aid of a survey. Regression analyses unveil the significant impact of biophilic design elements on perceived restorativeness. Notably, visual connections with nature, spacious environments, and a harmonious blend of complexity and order emerge as critical contributors to attention restoration. However, certain biophilic attributes, such as mystery and risk, exhibit unexpected negative impacts on perceived restorativeness. The study concludes that integrating biophilic design in hotels significantly shapes restorative spaces. The study suggests prioritizing visual connections with nature and creating spacious environments with well-ordered elements in hotel design. Moreover, it advocates exploring policy changes to promote the integration of biophilic design in future hotel development projects. These insights cater to the needs of hotel

designers, architects, and policymakers aiming to elevate guest experiences and overall well-being in the unique context of luxury hospitality.

Keywords: Biophilic Design, Luxury Hotels, Attention Restoration, Hospitality Industry, Nature Exposure

INTRODUCTION

The integration of biophilic strategies in the built environment has gained significant attention in recent years. A growing body of research has emphasized the link between exposure to nature and improved human health outcomes (Aerts et al., 2018; Gür & Kaprol, 2022; Nitu et al., 2022). These effects encompass physiological, psychological, and cognitive aspects. Spending time in nature, including around plants and sunlight, has been linked to feeling calmer, having lower blood pressure, and experiencing a more positive mood. (Romagosa et al., 2015). Natural environments have also been found to promote restoration from mental fatigue and improve cognitive performance (Joye & van den Berg, 2018). In the built environment, biophilic design seeks to recreate or incorporate elements of nature to bring aforementioned benefits to occupants (Richardson & Butler, 2022). This suggests the importance of connecting people with nature within indoor spaces, especially in urban environments where access to natural environments may be limited. Biophilic design principles encompass a wide range of strategies, including the use of natural materials, the incorporation of plants and water features, the integration of views to nature, and the maximization of daylight and ventilation (Kellert, 2018).

Research in various settings, such as workplaces, educational institutions, and healthcare facilities, have demonstrated the potential of biophilic design to improve productivity, creativity, and overall well-being of occupants (Kellert & Calabrese, 2015; Peters & D’Penna, 2020). However, the effectiveness and practical application of this concept in luxury hotels remain largely understudied. Understanding the potential benefits associated with its implementation in such settings is essential for

enhancing guest experiences and promoting well-being. Thus, the study aimed to assess the effect of integrating biophilic design strategies on attention restoration in hotels in Nigeria. It is pertinent to note, however, that this research does not seek to establish a causal relationship between these strategies and attention restoration. Rather, it examines specifically, the relationship and effectiveness of biophilic design principles on attention restoration within the context of the hospitality settings.

BACKGROUND STUDY

In our fast-paced, modern world, attention is a valuable and finite resource (Christie & Schrater, 2015). Attention restoration has become increasingly relevant, as individuals seek respite from the constant demands on their cognitive faculties. Restorative spaces are environments that can promote restoration and recovery from stress or mental fatigue (Peters & D’Penna, 2020). These spaces are characterized by their connection to nature and the presence of natural elements such as vegetation and water features. They provide a sense of calm and relaxation, allowing individuals to replenish their attentional resources and improve their overall well-being. The term ‘restorative spaces’ is derived from the work of Kaplan and Kaplan (1989).

Wilson (1984) posits that humans possess an inherent bond with nature which is not merely aesthetic; it has profound psychological and physiological impacts. Biophilic design leverages this to create environments that promote well-being. This positive impact on human health is well-documented: exposure to nature, has been associated with reduced stress, increased positive emotions, and enhanced cognitive functioning (Ulrich et al., 1991). These benefits extend to architectural spaces, where integrating nature-inspired elements can create restorative environments. Attention restoration, a key component of cognitive well-being, is also significantly influenced by natural elements (Purani & Kumar, 2018). Attention Restoration Theory (ART), advocates that exposure to nature or nature-like settings can restore directed attention, promoting mental clarity and cognitive rejuvenation. This restoration of attention is crucial in hotel buildings and environments, where guests often seek respite and relaxation.

Biophilic Design

The term 'biophilia' was coined in 1973 and developed by Wilson (1984) in his 'Biophilia hypothesis'. According to Wilson's, there is an intrinsic link between human mental health and the experience of immersion in a robust ecological environment. This outlook has been adopted by a wide range of researchers, including those in the design field who found strong evidence that the built environment can enhance human well-being by honouring the innate predisposition that humans have towards natural settings (Kellert, 1993).

A substantial body of research now supports the biophilia hypothesis (Browning et al., 2015). Different understanding branching in different directions have been proposed. Various studies have suggested different ways in which the principles of biophilia can be implemented in the built environment. Heerwagen and Gregory (2008) suggested that to implement biophilia in building design, designers first need to understand how nature creates certain feelings that supports well-being. After this understanding, the study claimed that designers must examine form, material, and space as means to integrate nature in the built environment. The study developed a design palette consisting of seven attributes to integrate biophilia into the built environment. Kellert (2018) also proposed a variety of different categorizations of biophilic principles. They suggested that people of different ages, cultures, and individual backgrounds might prioritize different biophilic values in different ways, but that the overall set of evolved needs and orientations in relation to nature should be understood as similar for all humans.

Recent studies provide evidence that biophilic design has tangible, beneficial effects on health. reinforcing the link between humans and nature and emphasizing its significance in both design research and practice. Despite a lack of clear implementation guidance, the importance of this connection is increasingly recognized. Building on this, Ryan et al. (2014) introduced a more contemporary and feasible framework for biophilic design that reflects the crucial nature-health relationships in the built environment. Browning et al. (2015) further elaborated on this framework: three categories and 14 patterns of biophilic design aligned with

nature-health relationships. The emphasis of Ryan et al. (2014) and Browning et al. (2015) lies on patterns that have shown evidence, to varying extents, of impacting cognitive capacity to improve and sustain a healthy life experience through an affinity with nature. Due to these myriads of studies and research on biophilic design, there exist many scales for measuring its presence, quality, and overall usage – because of the varying categorisations and attributes proposed by different studies. A comprehensive scale is that adopted by Asim and Shree (2019) which is based on the framework proposed by Browning et al. (2015). It divides biophilic patterns in three major categories; Nature in the Space (NIS), Natural Analogues (NATLOG) and Human Nature Relationship (HNR) as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Patterns of Biophilic design. Adapted from Asim and Shree (2019)

Design in Hospitality and Biophilic Hotel Settings

How the built environment is designed in service industries is often considered an aspect of marketing. A term frequently used in this context is “atmospherics,” - the intentional manipulation of the environment to influence consumer emotions and behaviours (Jani & Han, 2015). Atmospherics seeks to promote an aesthetic response based on feelings of connectedness, belonging, and a sense of discovery (Scannell & Gifford, 2017). These goals are roughly parallel to ART components. In service

industries, the environmental design is primarily focused on achieving patron loyalty and encouraging spending behaviours, but it can also be understood as providing a restorative benefit for patrons.

In recent years, biophilic theory has begun to exert an influence on the design of servicescape environments. Purani and Kumar (2018) conducted the first research study that specifically examined the biophilic attributes of servicescapes regarding their attention restoration benefits. Participants in this research were asked to examine images of different service contexts, including the lobby of a hospital, several different restaurants, a spa, and a bank lobby. Some of these environments incorporated biophilic design attributes, such as plants, natural light, and natural materials, while others were non-biophilic designs. The environments incorporating biophilic design elements were rated more highly by the participants in all categories. The study also found that employees working in service environments with biophilic design features reported significantly higher levels of productivity and job satisfaction. Rosenbaum et al. (2019) published another study exploring the retail environments as biophilic servicescapes.. Results revealed that patrons who experienced the biophilic servicescapes are more interested in the environment and setting, more involved and curious, more attentive, and emotionally attached than the patrons who experienced the servicescape without biophilic design features.

Alfakhri et al. (2018) studied a variety of features that contributed to customers' evaluation of hotels, ranging from financial considerations and quality of service to aesthetic and emotional responses to the environment. Among the design elements that emerged in this study, patrons often stressed the importance of colour, light, big windows, ease of wayfinding, comforting sounds, and the presence of plants and water. Many of these highly rated environmental features could be understood as aspects of biophilic design. Browning et al. (2012), and Green (2017) similarly found that biophilic design contributed to guests spending more time and money in hotel lobbies, lounges, retail, and restaurants. The observational study found that 36% of guests of the biophilic hotels used the lobbies while it was only 25% in conventional hotel lobbies (Browning et al., 2017). These studies provide general evidence that

features associated with biophilic design may have important benefits for hotel patrons, employees, and owners, but more research is needed to improve the empirical quality of this evidence and to test the human benefits of specific design components.

Attention Restoration Theory

Initially developed by Kaplan and Kaplan (1989), ART posits that individuals are subject to two different attention types: directed and involuntary attention. Directed attention is the conscious, effortful focus required for tasks like work, study, or problem-solving. It is susceptible to fatigue and can lead to a state of mental exhaustion. In contrast, involuntary attention is a more automatic and effortless form of attention. It arises when individuals engage with environments that are intrinsically fascinating and contain stimuli known as "soft fascination." ART proposes that exposure to natural or nature-like environments, characterized by soft fascination stimuli, promotes the restoration of directed attention (Sona et al., 2019).

The restorative process involves four principles. The first component is 'Being Away'. Natural settings create a sense of "being away" from one's usual environment and demands (Kaplan & Kaplan, 1989). The notion is that by avoiding well-worn mental content, one can prevent the need for directed attention to activate such content (Kaplan, 2001). Therefore, when one's attention is tired, it can be let to rest. This is the fundamental justification for the advantageous consequences of "getting away from it all." The second component is "fascination". According to Herzog et al. (2003), fascination is the state of being captivated or engrossed without effort. A setting that retains one's attention with little effort has fascination. The third component is the "extent" of the surroundings. A setting has extent if it contains enough content and structure that it can engage the mind long enough to enable focused attention to rest. Such locations are considered as being "whole other worlds" (Kaplan, 1995). The final component of restorative environments is "compatibility" with the interests, goals, and outlooks of an individual. An environment is compatible

if there is an alignment between an individual's aims or inclinations and the kinds of activities supported, promoted, or necessitated by the environment.

There exists a substantial amount of literature on the application of ART in different environments. Hartig et al. (1991) demonstrated that individuals who spent time in a natural environment reported feeling more restored and exhibited improved attentional capacities compared to those in urban settings. Similarly, Kaplan (1995) conducted a study involving university students, finding that nature walks enhanced cognitive functioning and restored directed attention. Similar to the study above, a huge number of previous studies on restorative environments using the ART model have mostly focused on large-scale outdoor urban settings (Berman et al., 2008; Berto et al., 2015; San Juan et al., 2017).

Of greater interest for the current study is previous studies that applied the ART model to interior environments and architectural studies. These studies are relatively rare in literature, but they provide compelling evidence supporting the principles of ART. A study by Evans & McCoy (1998) revealed that interior environments incorporating natural elements, such as indoor plants or nature-inspired artwork, led to improved cognitive performance and enhanced well-being. The study mentioned earlier by Tennessen and Cimprich (1995) and that of Ulrich's (1984) examined the impact of window views in hospital wards on individuals recuperating from surgery. They found that patients with views of nature experienced less pain, required fewer pain medications, and had shorter post-operative hospital stays compared to those with urban views. Felsten (2009), investigated the impact of large nature murals on attentionally fatigued college students within classroom settings. The study concluded that direct exposure to nature, or the presence of large nature murals, was indeed restorative for students. A subsequent investigation by Moreno et al. (2018) took a unique approach by developing the "Calm Spot" app, applying ART in the classroom environment. This study introduces the innovative concept of technology-driven nature integration in classrooms, showcasing the potential benefits and the need for its careful implementation.

A number of scales have been devised to evaluate the restorative qualities of natural or nature-like environments, including the Restorative Components Scale (RES; Laumann et al., 2001), the Perceived Restorativeness Scale (PRS; Korpela and Hartig, 1996), and the Restoration Scale (RS; Han, 2003). Other scales are also in existence some of which are modifications or combinations of others (Han, 2018). For this study, the PRS stands out as a robust and relevant choice for assessing the restorative potential of environments, especially from the perspective of ART. It was developed to quantify the restorative quality of the environment through examining the depth of the four restorativeness factors: (Asim et al., 2020; Joye, 2007). By assessing the presence or absence of these factors, the PRS provides a measure of the extent to which a building or space can offer a restorative experience.

Theoretical Framework

This review recognises the relevance of various environmental theories in the context of biophilic design within the built environment as identified by Peters & D’Penna (2020) and Zhong et al., (2022). This study adopts the relationship between biophilic design and ART as a conceptual framework for the research. It most suits a study in a hospitality environment and has been employed previously by various research in similar environments (Lee et al., 2023; Purani & Kumar, 2018; Song et al., 2022).

Figure 2: Conceptual framework for the study.

While existing literature has acknowledged the positive impact of biophilic design strategies on attention restoration within various contexts, a significant gap exists in the comprehensive exploration of these strategies within the specific domain of

hotels, especially in the Nigerian context. Most studies in this area have tended to focus on specific components such as lobbies, and interior spaces, leaving a dearth of research that assesses the integration of biophilic design throughout the hotels. The absence of a holistic examination represents a significant gap in the current literature. Addressing these gaps is imperative for developing an in-depth knowledge of the relationship between biophilic design and attention restoration in hotels.

METHODOLOGY

This research adopts a quantitative approach, specifically employing a correlational design to examine the correlation between biophilic design strategies and attention restoration in hotels. The objectives of the study revolve around examining the association between the two concepts. Consequently, a quantitative approach is most appropriate. Using a survey was considered appropriate to meet the goals of this research, as it enables straightforward definition and measurement of variables, along with assessing their relationships.

To obtain a representative sample, a random sampling method is employed. The sample population for this study consists of adults aged 18 and above who have recently stayed in hotels in Abuja for at least one night. These individuals represent the target population of hotel guests who have experienced the hotel environment, making them suitable respondents. These individuals possess valuable knowledge pertinent to the study's objectives. The approach involved utilizing social media, primarily WhatsApp, Facebook, and Twitter, to identify and engage with relevant groups and connections. Personal networks were also leveraged to broaden the pool of potential respondents. The inclusion criteria ensure that the sample is relevant to the study's objectives. In cases where participants didn't fully fit into the criteria, they were encouraged to share the survey with others possessing the required experience. The questionnaire was divided into three sections. The first enquired about the demographic data of the participants and the second section employed a modified version of the Biophilic Environment Variables (BEVs) used by Asim and Shree (2019). The final section of the questionnaire used the Perceived Restorativeness

Scale (PRS) developed by Hartig et al. (1997). The questionnaire also underwent pre-testing with a small group of respondents, ensuring clarity in the phrasing of the questions and predefined responses.

The platform used for data collection made it easy to organise, sort and code the data with Microsoft Excel. This was also used for the descriptive analyses. Nevertheless, for interpreting the Likert and ranking scales in subsequent sections of the survey, inferential statistical analysis becomes necessary. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to perform regression analysis to establish the association between the measured metrics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The survey utilized established survey scales to collect data from the respondents. The internal consistency results for the modified Biophilic Environment Variables (BEVs) and the Perceived Restorativeness Scale (PRS) indicate a high level of internal consistency for both scales, as evidenced by the Cronbach's Alpha values of 0.928 and 0.861, respectively.

Out of the 434 responses collected in the survey, 415 were deemed useful for analysis after coding and cleaning. The demographic analyses of the respondents provide valuable insights into the respondents in the study. Most respondents fall within the younger age brackets, with people below the age of 35 comprising nearly two-thirds of the sample. The sample is also slightly biased towards males, comprising 57.3% of the respondents. However, the difference is not stark, indicating a relatively balanced representation of both genders in the study. Furthermore, the cultural background distribution showcases a predominantly Nigerian respondent. Nonetheless, the inclusion of respondents from other West African and African backgrounds adds a broader spectrum of perspectives. An overwhelming portion (76.4%) holding at least a tertiary education degree suggesting that the sample comprises individuals with a certain level of intellectual capacity to understand the concepts of biophilic design and attention restoration.

Establishing biophilic design strategies

The preliminary set of analyses carried out were to establish the presence of biophilic design strategies in the hotels. This was achieved with a descriptive statistic of both the BEVs and the PRS variables (Further analysis, through linear regression, was used to determine the specific impact of the BEVs on perceived restorativeness and to identify which strategies contribute most significantly to attention restoration in the hotel spaces.

Table 1). The mean scores for the BEVs indicate moderate to high levels of perceived biophilic design elements within the hotel spaces. Notably, respondents reported relatively strong visual connections with nature ($M = 4.37$, $SD = 1.886$), moderate levels of non-visual connections with nature, connections with natural systems, nature and comfort, light, and space within the hotel environments. The summed scores for NIS, NATLOG, and HNR also indicate a substantial presence of biophilic elements in the hotel design. On the other hand, the PRS variables suggest that respondents generally perceive the hotel environments as moderately restorative. Their summed scores indicate moderate to high levels of perceived restorativeness, with particularly strong scores in Extent.

Further analysis, through linear regression, was used to determine the specific impact of the BEVs on perceived restorativeness and to identify which strategies contribute most significantly to attention restoration in the hotel spaces.

Table 1: Presence of the biophilic strategies and PRS variables in the hotels

		Min.	Max.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Biophilic Environment	1. Visual Connection with Nature	1	8	4.37	1.886
	2. Non-Visual Connection with Nature	0	4	2.07	1.147
	3. Connection with Natural Systems	0	4	2.02	1.015
	4. Nature and Comfort	0	5	2.30	1.123

	5. Light	1	4	2.24	1.169
	6. Space	1	6	3.53	1.525
	Σ (1-6): Nature in the Space (NIS)	3	31	16.54	7.87
	7. Natural Shapes & Forms	0	6	2.00	1.308
	8. Material Connection with Nature	0	4	2.10	1.185
	9. Complexity & Order	0	4	2.24	1.153
	Σ (7-9): Natural Analogues (NATLOG)	0	14	6.34	3.65
	10. Preservation & Place-making	0	4	2.13	1.145
	11. Prospect & Refuge	0	4	2.42	1.085
	12. Mystery & Risk/Peril	0	4	1.92	1.154
	Σ (10-12): Human-Nature Relationship (HNR)	0	12	6.47	3.38
PRS Variables	Σ Being Away	0	12	5.79	3.184
	Σ Fascination	0	30	15.22	8.102
	Σ Extent	0	24	16.13	6.148
	Σ Compatibility	0	30	14.11	7.841

Effect of Biophilic Designs on Attention Restoration

The linear regression results (

Table 2) offer valuable insights into the relationships between different biophilic design elements and perceived restorativeness in the reported hotel spaces.

In the NIS category, Visual Connection with Nature showed a significant positive effect on Being Away ($\beta = 0.028$, $p < 0.01$) and Fascination ($\beta = 0.044$, $p < 0.01$), implying that as the visual connection with nature increases, guests are more likely to feel a sense of being away from their usual ‘draining’ environment and experience fascination in the hotel space. Non-Visual Connection with Nature exhibits a positive effect on Compatibility, suggesting that enhancing non-visual connections contributes to increased sense of compatibility with intended actions in the environment. Notably, Connection with Natural Systems has a statistically significant negative

effect on Extent ($\beta = -0.184$). This indicates that a stronger connection with natural systems may be linked with a perceived limitation in the extent of the restorative environment. Nature and Comfort showed no significant effects on any PRS variables. Light and Space showed varying positive effects on Being Away, Fascination, and Compatibility. These stress the importance of careful consideration of lighting and spatial design in promoting particular elements of perceived restorativeness, like being away and fascination.

Under NATLOG, Complexity & Order stood out with positive effects on Fascination and Compatibility. This suggests that mixing in natural shapes, forms, and order in the design contributes significantly to its fascination and perceived compatibility. However, Natural Shapes & Forms has significant negative impact on Compatibility ($\beta = -0.100$), suggesting that a focus on natural shapes alone may not align with guests' perceived compatibility.

The HNR category revealed notable findings, particularly with Prospect & Refuge, which has positive effects on all PRS variables. This implies that aspects balancing prospect and refuge contribute significantly to guests' feeling of restoration. Conversely, Preservation & Place-making shows no significant effects on any PRS variables. Mystery & Risk/Peril exhibits a significant negative effect on Extent ($\beta = -0.291$), suggesting that an increased sense of mystery and risk may be associated with a perception of reduced extent in the restorative environment.

The overall model fit (indicated by the Adjusted R^2 values with all $p < 0.01$) suggest that the included BEVs explain a significant portion of the variance in the PRS variables.

Table 2: Regression result of the effect of BEV on PRS; standardized β coefficients

PRS Variables				
Biophilic Environment Variables	Being Away	Fascination	Extent	Compatibility

	Visual Connection with Nature	**0.028	**0.044	-0.111	*0.040
	Non-Visual Connection with Nature	0.073	0.075	-0.042	**0.156
	Connection with Natural Systems	-0.009	0.041	** -0.184	0.069
	Nature and Comfort	0.087	0.027	0.094	0.007
	Light	*0.049	*0.029	-0.019	0.066
NIS	Space	**0.147	**0.130	-0.020	**0.176
	Natural Shapes & Forms	0.000	*-0.100	-0.010	-0.071
	Material Connection with Nature	0.024	0.044	-0.024	*-0.069
NATLOG	Complexity & Order	0.057	**0.194	0.042	**0.174
	Preservation & Place-making	0.081	0.064	-0.059	0.059
	Prospect & Refuge	*0.103	*0.109	**0.201	*0.107
HNR	Mystery & Risk/Peril	0.052	0.069	** -0.291	0.053
	Adjusted R ² square	**0.250	**0.293	**0.164	**0.337

Note: ** $p < 0.01$ (significant effect); * $p < 0.05$ (marginal effect)

CONCLUSIONS

Key findings from the study include that there was overall statistically significant impact of biophilic design strategies on creating restorative spaces. Creating visual connection with nature, spacious environments, and the careful balance of complexity & order emerged as pivotal contributors to attention restoration in hotels. These findings resonate with previous studies and contribute valuable insights to the existing body of knowledge in biophilic design, architecture, and hospitality literature. By emphasizing the significance of these strategies, this study provides a practical framework for hotel designers to enhance the well-being and satisfaction of

guests. Based on this, several actionable recommendations can be proposed. Firstly, hotel designers and architects should prioritize incorporating visual connections with nature, spacious environments with ordered and hierarchical elements in their design plans. This can be achieved through strategic placement of windows to maximize natural views, creating open and uncluttered spaces, and integrating diverse and ordered natural elements such as plants and textured materials. It is also advised to explore potential policy changes or improvements that promote the integration of biophilic design in hotel development projects. This could involve advocating for incentives or regulations that incentivize sustainable and nature-centric design practices in the hospitality sector.

Future studies can benefit from incorporating objective measures of attention restoration, such as physiological responses or behavioural observations, to complement the self-reported survey. Lastly, investigating the influence of individual differences, such as age, gender, and cultural background, can further enrich the literature.

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